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Identifying driving forces and barriers in implementation of Industry 4.0

Employee survey results of five Slovak companies

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Abstract

Understanding the driving forces and barriers in implementation of Industry 4.0 is a fundamental step to understand the digital divide at organizational level, and to build a conceptual framework for solving it. This working paper is a piece in this ongoing investigation by describing the results of a survey filled by the employees of five companies in Slovakia. The main contribution of the research is a detailed description of the employees' perception of the implementation of digital solutions.

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1. Introduction

Industry 4.0 is reshaping the manufacturing environment through the integration of advanced digital technologies. This change is characterized by the use of cyber-physical systems, the Internet of Things (IoT), big data analytics, artificial intelligence (AI) and cloud computing what leads to development of smart factories and highly efficient manufacturing processes (Frank et al., 2019). The purpose of Industry 4.0 is in potential to significantly increase productivity, flexibility, and sustainability in manufacturing, thereby support innovation and competitive advantage (Dev et al., 2020; Stock & Seliger, 2016).

Despite the clear advantages, the implementation of Industry 4.0 technologies is full of challenges. Firms must overcome significant barriers, including high initial costs, data security concerns, and the need for a skilled workforce that is expert in managing and maintaining these advanced systems (Frank et al., 2019; Ghobakhloo, 2018). Understanding these drivers and barriers is critical to successful adoption, particularly in specific national contexts where economic, cultural and regulatory factors may play a significant role. In the Slovak Republic, the industrial sector is an important part of the national economy, with industrial production representing a significant share of the country's GDP.

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As such, the implementation of Industry 4.0 technologies could provide significant competitive advantages and economic benefits. However, the extent to which Slovak companies adopt these technologies and the specific factors and barriers they face remain insufficiently researched, although, some studies provide insights into the challenges and strategic approaches necessary for implementing Industry 4.0 in Slovak SMEs, especially within broader regional contexts (Vacek et al., 2022). To fill this research gap, the following chapters present the results of a questionnaire survey of employees in five Slovak companies in the form of five separate case studies.

2. Case study 1

2.1. Company background

The history of parent company brand began in 1948 in Italia. As in most cases, the beginnings were modest, a small artisan workshop was primarily concerned with the production of smaller brass components. The fifties were all about hard work and perseverance. Thanks to this, the brand already in 1968, as the only manufacturer in its field, established a laboratory for testing the quality of its own products, which later found application in many technological researches and modernizations. Currently, company has 3 production plants in Italy, employs more than 950 people, and with a capacity of 80 tons of processed brass per day ranks among the largest production companies in the field of technological solutions for air conditioning, heating, and intelligent systems. It was mainly persistence, diligence and high quality of products that earned firm a place among the leading European manufacturers in the field of heating technology, in which it has been operating for almost 70 years.

The Slovak branch of this family company from Italy began to present its history in 1994, when a trading company was founded with the aim of distributing components of this Italian brand on the Slovak market. Currently, this family business employs 19 employees in the positions of economist, business director, manager of logistics, sales, trade, marketing, sales representatives and warehouse manager. The previous premises were no longer sufficient for storage capacities due to increasing sales, so the company built its new, business premises and logistics center in 2023. From this warehouse, they can also supply the surrounding countries without any problems.

2.2. Employee demographics

Figure 1 provides a visual representation of the gender composition within the company. The chart is divided into two segments, each representing the number and percentage of male and female employees. The blue segment, which represents male employees, comprises 13 individuals. This accounts for approximately 68.42% of the total workforce. This indicates that a significant portion of the workforce is male. The orange segment denotes female employees, consisting of 6 individuals. This makes up about 31.58% of the total workforce. This shows that there are fewer female employees compared to their male counterparts.

To summarize, the chart reveals that the workforce is predominantly male, with 13 male employees making up 68.42% of the workforce, compared to 6 female employees who constitute 31.58% of the workforce. This distribution highlights a gender imbalance within the company, where males constitute a larger proportion of staff.

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Figure 1

Gender distribution of employees

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 2

Age distribution of employees

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 2 shows us a visual representation of the proportions of employees across four different age groups. Each segment of the chart represents a specific age range, identified by both color and percentage. The largest segment, depicted by the orange color, illustrates employees aged 26-35. This group consists of 8 individuals, representing approximately 42.1% of the workforce. This suggests that a significant portion of the employees are in their mid-career stages. The gray segment, illustrating employees aged 36-45 years, also comprises 8 individuals, which represents 42.1% of the total employees in the company. This indicates that another substantial portion of the workforce falls within this age range. The yellow segment, representing employees aged 46-65 years, includes 2 individuals, accounting for approximately 10.5% of the workforce.

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This shows a smaller representation of employees in this older age range. Finally, the blue segment involves 1 employee aged 18-25 years, who fits into 5.3% of the staff working in this company. This indicates that the youngest age group is the least represented among the employees.

To sum it up, the age distribution of employees reveals that the majority of the workforce is composed of individuals in the 26-35 and 36-45 age ranges, each constituting about 42.1% of the total workforce. Employees in the 46-65 age range make up 10.5% of the workforce, while the youngest group, aged 18-25, comprises 5.3%. This distribution indicates a workforce with a strong presence of mid-career professionals and fewer employees in the early and later stages of their careers. After examining the demographic structure of the company's employees, we will look at the current state of digitization within the company.

2.3. Current state of digitization

In recent years, the company in Italy as well as in Slovakia has moved significantly towards the digitization of its business processes and activities. The elimination of paper correspondence is already common nowadays, but the subsequent extraction of data from it and the subsequent analysis of this data for further use is not yet established in every company. For internal company communication, this company works with Office 365 cloud service, which allows them to share files and back up smaller files as a precaution against the possible failure of their computers. In this company, they have been using the ERP system for a long time, which they have changed twice due to insufficient functions, and they are gradually introducing several technologies from the well-known Industry 4.0 concept.

Nowadays company tries to automate repetitive tasks, to use chatbots again for customer support and to decrease the workload of our employees by mitigating tasks than can be automated. An important part that the company is actively working on as part of innovation is more efficient logistics in the new, significantly larger warehouse that they were used to.

2.4. Employees' perception of the implementation of digital solutions

Figure 3 illustrates the different experiences employees perceived in activities related to the implementation of digital solutions. It is important to notice, that company is at this time only in an early stage, and trying to find the best solution. The chart is divided into three categories: smooth and effective, with complications, and very problematic and complicated. The largest portion of the pie chart, colored blue and accounting for 84% of the responses (16 out of 19), represents the experience described as "Smooth and effective." This indicates that the majority of respondents found the digital solutions implementation process so far to be efficient and successful without significant issues. The second segment, depicted in orange and constituting 16% of the responses (3 out of 19), corresponds to the category "With complications." This shows that a minority of respondents encountered some issues during the preparation for implementation, though it was not highly problematic.

Notably, the chart does not contain any segment for "Very problematic and complicated," indicated by the white section marked with a zero, suggesting that none of the respondents found the digital solutions implementation process so far to be highly challenging or complicated.

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Figure 3

Employees' perception of the implementation of digital solutions

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

To sum it up, the chart highlights that most employees in this company experienced a smooth and effective implementation of their digital solutions so far, while a smaller percentage faced some complications, and none reported severe difficulties. It is important to remind, that company is just in an early phase and trying to find best solution.

Figure 4

Changes in processes since the first start of Industry 4.0 technologies implementation

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 4 depicts different perceptions of process changes after implementing Industry 4.0 technologies among employees. The chart is divided into three categories: mostly negative changes, no noticed changes, and positive changes. The largest segment, colored grey and representing 68% of the responses (13 out of 19), shows that most of respondents have noticed positive changes in the processes since the implementation of Industry 4.0 technologies.

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Blue segment accounts for 32% of the responses (6 out of 19) and corresponds to those who reported mostly negative changes. This highlights that a significant minority experienced unfavorable outcomes from the technological implementation. It is interesting that there is no orange segment on the chart, indicating that none of the respondents selected the option of not noticing any changes.

To sum it up, the chart shows that a majority of employees have experienced positive changes, while a considerable portion has faced negative changes, with no respondents reporting an absence of noticeable changes.

Figure 5
Effectiveness of the current ERP system

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 5 illustrates the perceptions of respondents regarding the effectiveness of their current Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system. The chart is divided into three categories: ineffective, moderately effective, and very effective. The largest segment, colored grey and representing 79% of the responses (15 out of 19), indicates that the majority of respondents find the current ERP system to be very effective. This highlights a high level of satisfaction with the system's performance among most respondents. The blue segment makes 10,5% of the responses (2 out of 19) and corresponds to those who reported the ERP system as ineffective. This suggests that a small part of the respondents is dissatisfied with the system's effectiveness.

Segment colored by orange color also represents 10,5% of the responses (2 out of 19) and denotes those who find the ERP system to be moderately effective. This indicates that an equal number of respondents have a neutral stance on the system's effectiveness. To sum it up, the chart shows that the majority of respondents perceive their current ERP system as very effective, while smaller portions view it as either moderately effective or ineffective.

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Figure 6

Impact of the current ERP system on process tracking and inventory management

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 6 describes the different perceptions of employees regarding the effectiveness of their current ERP system in managing processes and inventory. The chart is divided into three categories: significantly improves overview, provides some benefits but is not ideal, and has minimal impact. The largest segment, colored blue and representing 84,2 % of the responses (16 out of 19), indicates that the majority of respondents believe the current ERP system significantly improves the overview of process tracking and inventory management. This highlights a strong positive impact of the ERP system on these aspects. The orange segment accounts for 15,8 % of the responses (3 out of 19) and corresponds to respondents who feel that the ERP system provides some benefits but is not ideal. This suggests that while the system is beneficial, it still has option for improvement according to a minority of respondents. There is no grey segment on the chart, as indicated by the absence of responses in this category, what means that none of the respondents believe that the ERP system has minimal impact on process tracking and inventory management. To sum it up, the chart shows that the vast majority of respondents perceive their current ERP system as significantly improving process tracking and inventory management, while a smaller portion acknowledges some benefits but sees potential for further improvement.

Figure 7 describes the perceptions of employees regarding how cloud solutions affect efficiency in their processes at work. The chart is divided into three categories: provides some benefits but also has disadvantages, has minimal impact, and significantly simplifies and accelerates processes. The largest segment, depicted by grey color representing 73,6 % of the responses (14 out of 19), indicates that the majority of respondents believe the cloud solution significantly simplifies and accelerates processes. This highlights a strong positive impact of cloud solutions on efficiency. The blue segment accounts for 15,9 % of the employees (3 out of 19) and refers to those who feel that the cloud solution provides some benefits but also has disadvantages.

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This suggests that while cloud solutions offer advantages, they are not without their drawbacks according to a minority of respondents. The orange segment represents 10,5 % of the responses (2 out of 19) and indicates those who believe the cloud solution has minimal impact on efficiency. This indicates that a small portion of respondents do not see significant benefits from the cloud solution.

Figure 7
The impact of cloud solution on work efficiency

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 8
Utilization and reach of artificial intelligence

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

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Figure 8 describes various applications of artificial intelligence (AI) within the employees' operations. The chart is divided into 6 categories: demand prediction and service planning, personalized recommendations for B2B, optimization of logistics processes, automation of tasks in administration and hotline, creating and managing chatbots for customer service, and a category for those who do not know. The largest segment, colored grey and representing 52,6 % of the responses (10 out of 19), indicates that the majority of respondents are using AI for the optimization of logistics processes. This highlights a significant focus on improving logistics efficiency through AI. The yellow segment accounts for 36,8 % of the responses (7 out of 19) and corresponds to those using AI for the automation of tasks in administration and hotline. This shows a considerable use of AI in streamlining administrative tasks and improving hotline efficiency. The orange segment represents 5,3 % of the responses (1 out of 19) and denotes the use of AI for personalized recommendations for B2B. This shows a more limited but specific application of AI in enhancing business-to-business interactions.

The dark blue segment, representing 5,3 % of the responses (1 out of 19), corresponds to the use of AI for demand prediction and service planning. This suggests a focus on leveraging AI for forecasting and planning purposes. The light blue segment represents 0% of the responses (0 out of 19) and indicates that none of the respondents are using AI for creating and managing chatbots for customer service. The green segment also represents 0% of the responses (0 out of 19), showing that none of the respondents selected the option of not knowing about AI utilization.

In conclusion, the chart shows that the majority of respondents use AI for optimizing logistics processes and automating administrative tasks, with smaller portions applying AI to personalized recommendations for B2B and demand prediction.

3. Case study 2

3.1. Company background

The company started as a small family business established in 1992 and since 2006 became an international company and expanded to other EU countries as well. Ownership of company is pure Slovak. Their mindset is set to stay in line with the most modern approaches, certification norms and methods. Key business activities cover the complex management of fire protection of buildings, which partially consists of analysis, proposal of the best solution, monitoring, evaluation and lifelong maintenance. Their teams ensure that assets of clients are protected with reliable systems.

Main vision in future is to become the best plumbing fire system, supplier of fire and rescue equipment and a leader in the European market. More than 70 people work in their Slovak business unit and company provides their services with stable operation also in other EU countries.

3.2. Employee demographics

Figure 9 provides a visual representation of the gender composition within an organization. The chart is divided into two segments, each representing the number of male and female employees respectively. The larger segment, colored in blue, signifies the male employees, who make up a substantial majority of the workforce.

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Specifically, there are 48 male employees, which translates to approximately 79% of the total employee structure. This dominant proportion underscores the significant presence of male employees in the organization. In contrast, the smaller segment, depicted in orange, represents the female employees. There are 13 female employees, comprising about 21% of the total workforce. This smaller percentage highlights the relatively lower number of female employees compared to their male counterparts. Overall, the chart clearly illustrates a pronounced gender difference in the organization, with male employees significantly outranking female employees. The use of distinct colors and numerical labels within the chart aids in easily understanding the gender distribution and its proportions in percentage terms.

Figure 9
Gender distribution of employees

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 10
Age distribution of employees

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

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Figure 10 shows the age distribution of employees within the organization. The chart is segmented into four distinct age groups, each represented by different colors: blue for ages 18-25, orange for ages 26-35, gray for ages 36-45, and yellow for ages 46-55. The largest segment, shown in orange, represents employees aged 26-35. This group comprises 23 employees, making up approximately 38% of the total workforce. This indicates that the organization has a relatively young employees, with a significant portion in their late twenties to mid-thirties. The blue segment represents employees aged 18-25, consisting of 21 employees. This age group accounts for about 34% of the workforce. This further emphasizes the youthful nature of the organization, with more than a third of employees being in their early career stages. The gray segment signifies the employees aged 36-45. There are 13 employees in this category, representing roughly 21% of the total employees. This suggests a moderate presence of mid-career professionals within the organization. The smallest segment, depicted in yellow, represents employees aged 46-55. This age group includes 4 employees, making up about 7% of the workforce. This indicates a relatively low number of staff who are in the later stages of their careers. Overall, this diagram illustrates a workforce predominantly composed of younger employees, with the largest groups being those in the 18-25 and 26-35 age ranges. The presence of older age groups decreases progressively, what highlights a potential focus on younger employee within the organization.

3.3. Current state of digitization

The company is currently in a phase where they use electronic data exchange via the Electronic document interchange (EDI) protocol and have mostly paperless workflow. Before establishing this kind of communication, they needed to change the way of billing from paper format to electronic among all suppliers, partners and experienced misunderstanding for the change. The use of EDI benefits from receiving documents in automatic mode, which means that there is no need for manual data entry. This leads to fewer errors and inaccuracies.

Electronic documents transferred via EDI are automatically processed as well as archived, and thanks to this, the company reduces the costs of paper document management. EDI speeds up the overall business process, enabling automatic control of orders, recording of letters and invoices, as well as shortening order and delivery times.

Due to the fact that after approximately 3 months of using automatic processing and accounting documentation, the company felt a reduction in error rates and a lower workload in this area, they decided on their own initiative to study the issue of Industry 4.0 concept and the potential benefits that its implementation could have for the company.

3.4. Employees' perception of the implementation of digital solutions

Figure 11 visually depicts the distribution of employee experiences during the implementation of an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system within the organization. The chart is divided into three segments, each corresponding to different levels of implementation experience: smooth and effective, with complications, and very problematic and complicated.

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Figure 11

Employees' perception of the implementation of digital solutions

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

The largest segment, colored in blue, indicates that the ERP system implementation was "Smooth and effective" for the majority of employees. This segment includes 44 employees, which accounts for approximately 73% of the total respondents. This substantial majority reflects a predominantly positive experience, suggesting that the implementation process was well-managed and efficiently executed for most employees. It also indicates that the system likely met its intended objectives and was integrated seamlessly into existing workflows. The second largest segment, in orange, represents employees who experienced the implementation process "With complications." There are 12 employees in this category, making up about 20% of the respondents. This indicates that while the implementation was ultimately successful, it was not without its challenges. These complications could range from technical issues to resistance to change, highlighting areas that may need attention or improvement in future implementations. The smallest segment, in grey, represents employees who found the implementation "Very problematic and complicated." This group includes 5 employees, constituting roughly 7% of the respondents. This minority suggests that a small portion of the workforce faced significant difficulties during the ERP system implementation. These challenges could have stemmed from major technical glitches, inadequate training, or substantial disruption to their usual workflows. Overall, the pie chart reveals that the implementation of the ERP system was generally smooth and effective for the majority of employees, with a smaller portion experiencing complications and an even smaller group facing significant issues. This distribution indicates a largely successful implementation process, with some options for improvement in managing complications and minimizing disruptions for all employees.

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Figure 12

Changes in processes since the first start of Industry 4.0 technologies implementation

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 12 6 illustrates the distribution of employee perceptions regarding process changes following the onset of digitalization within the organization. The chart is segmented into three categories, each representing a different perception of the changes. The largest segment, colored in grey, represents employees who have noticed positive changes since the start of digitalization. This group comprises 48 employees, making up approximately 79% of the total respondents. This significant majority indicates a widespread recognition of the benefits brought about by digitalization, reflecting a largely positive impact on organizational processes. The orange segment signifies employees who have not noticed any changes in processes. There are 11 employees in this category, accounting for about 18% of the total respondents. This suggests that a notable minority of the workforce has not perceived any significant changes, which may point to either a stable working environment for these individuals or a need for better communication about the changes implemented.

The smallest segment, colored in blue, represents employees who believe that the changes have been mostly negative. This group includes 2 employees, making up roughly 3% of the total respondents. This minimal percentage indicates a very small fraction of the workforce perceives digitalization negatively, suggesting that the adverse effects of digitalization are limited or isolated. Overall, the pie chart highlights a predominantly positive reception towards digitalization within the organization, with a vast majority recognizing improvements in processes. The distribution of responses provides valuable insights into employee experiences and the overall impact of digitalization efforts.

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Figure 13

Effectiveness of the current ERP system

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 13 describes the distribution of opinions on the effectiveness of their current ERP system. The chart is segmented into three distinct sections, each marked with a specific color and labeled with corresponding effectiveness levels. The grey section is the largest, consisting of 32 respondents. These respondents regard the ERP system as very effective, implying that it significantly improves their processes, meets their expectations, and provides considerable value to their operations. The orange section shows that 17 respondents consider the ERP system to be moderately effective. This suggests that these users perceive some benefits from the system, although it may not fully satisfy all their requirements or deliver optimal performance. 12 respondents represented by blue section believe that the ERP system is ineffective. This indicates a minority of the participants find the system does not meet their needs or fails to enhance their operational efficiency.

To sum it up, this pie chart finds that a majority of respondents find the ERP system effective to varying degrees, with 32 rating it as very effective, 17 as moderately effective, and 12 as ineffective. This distribution highlights a generally positive reception of the ERP system, albeit with room for improvement as indicated by the combined 29 respondents who see it as either moderately effective or ineffective.

Figure 14 shows a visual representation of employee perceptions regarding the effectiveness of the ERP system in enhancing process tracking and inventory management within the organization. The chart is divided into three segments, each reflecting a different level of perceived impact: significantly improves overview, provides some benefits but is not ideal, and has minimal impact.

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Figure 14

Impact of the current ERP system on process tracking and inventory management

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

The largest segment, colored in blue, represents the opinion that the ERP system "Significantly improves overview." This segment includes the majority of respondents, indicating that a substantial 91% of the employees (based on 56 respondents) believe that the ERP system has greatly enhanced their ability to track processes and manage inventory. This dominant view suggests that the ERP system is highly effective in providing comprehensive visibility and control over these critical functions, leading to better decision-making and operational efficiency. The second largest segment, in orange, signifies the perception that the ERP system "Provides some benefits but is not ideal." This segment includes a small portion of the respondents, accounting for approximately 7% of the total (based on 4 respondents).

This indicates that while these employees recognize some advantages of the ERP system, they also see options for improvement. This could reflect partial fulfillment of expectations or areas where the system could be more user-friendly or robust. The smallest segment, in grey, represents the opinion that the ERP system "Has minimal impact." This segment includes the smallest number of respondents, making up roughly 2% of the total (based on 1 respondent). This minimal percentage suggests that only a very small fraction of employees perceive the ERP system as having little to no effect on process tracking and inventory management.

This minority view may indicate isolated cases of inadequate system performance or specific challenges faced by these employees. In summary, the pie chart illustrates that the ERP system is overwhelmingly seen as a significant improvement for process tracking and inventory management, with a large majority of employees affirming its positive impact. The chart also highlights a smaller group that sees some benefits but suggests potential areas for further enhancement.

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Figure 15
The impact of cloud solution on work efficiency

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 15 describes the distribution of respondents' opinions on how cloud solutions affect their work efficiency. The chart is divided into three distinct segments, each associated with a different color and labeled with corresponding effectiveness levels. 45 respondents represented by the grey section, believe that the cloud solution significantly simplifies and accelerates their work processes. This indicates a strong positive impact, with the majority of participants finding that cloud technology greatly enhances their efficiency by providing seamless access to data, reliable backups, and improved collaboration tools. The blue segment denotes that 10 respondents recognize some advantages of the cloud solution but also note certain drawbacks. These might include concerns about data security, dependence on internet connectivity, or recurring costs associated with cloud services. This group acknowledges the mixed impact of cloud solutions, balancing both positive and negative aspects. The orange section represents 6 respondents who feel that the cloud solution has minimal impact on their work efficiency. These respondents might not see significant improvements or may rely more heavily on other tools and systems for their daily operations.

To sum it up, chart reveals that the majority of respondents (45) find the cloud solution significantly beneficial, greatly simplifying and accelerating their work processes. A smaller group (10) perceives the cloud solution as having both benefits and disadvantages, while the smallest group (6) believes it has minimal impact on their work efficiency. This distribution highlights a predominantly positive reception of cloud solutions, with most users experiencing enhanced efficiency, though some remain cautious about its drawbacks.

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Figure 16

Utilization and reach of artificial intelligence

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 16 visually represents how employees perceive the application of artificial intelligence (AI) within their organization. The chart is divided into six distinct segments, each reflecting a different area where AI is being implemented or acknowledged.

The largest segment, colored in yellow, represents the utilization of AI for "Automation of tasks in administration and support." This segment includes 29 respondents, making up approximately 48% of the total responses. This indicates that nearly half of the employees recognize AI's significant role in streamlining administrative tasks and enhancing support functions, thereby improving operational efficiency and reducing manual workloads. The second-largest segment, in grey, signifies employees who responded that AI is mostly used for optimization of logistics processes. This category includes 13 respondents, accounting for about 22% of the total. The orange segment represents the use of AI for "Personalized recommendations for customers." There are 11 respondents in this category, making up roughly 18% of the total responses. This indicates that a notable minority of employees are aware of AI's application in enhancing customer experiences through personalized services and recommendations, which is critical for customer satisfaction and retention.

The blue segment represents "Demand prediction and production planning," with 7 respondents, constituting about 12% of the total. This smaller percentage indicates that fewer employees recognize the role of AI in forecasting demand and optimizing production schedules, though it remains an important area where AI can drive significant efficiencies and improvements. The smallest segments, in light blue represent "Creating and managing chatbot for customer service". The small percentage of recognition in these areas suggests limited awareness or less prominent implementation of AI in customer service functions within the organization. To sum the results up, the pie chart illustrates that the predominant recognition of

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AI's utility is in automating administrative and support tasks. The distribution of responses underscores the need for increased awareness and communication about the diverse applications of AI, particularly in areas like customer service chatbots, to ensure employees are fully informed about the technology's potential benefits and current uses within their organization.

4. Case study 3

4.1. Company background

There are more than 1,700 mineral springs in Slovak republic and several companies provide bottled mineral water from them. We focused on the company that was founded in 1995 as the successor of the originally state-owned company, which was involved in capturing spring water in Slovakia.

This family company has a strong tradition, low turnover of employees who often work there until retirement age. The company focuses on the use of modern technologies, filling and packaging lines as well as systems for processing data and processes.

4.2. Employee demographics

Figure 17

Gender distribution of employees

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 17 illustrates the gender composition within the organization. The chart is divided into two segments, representing male and female employees, each depicted by different colors. The larger segment, colored in blue, represents male employees. This segment includes 52 individuals, which accounts for approximately 63.4% of the total workforce. This significant proportion indicates that male employees constitute a substantial majority within the organization. The predominance of male employees could reflect historical hiring practices, industry trends, or other factors influencing gender distribution. The orange segment signifies female employees. There are 30 individuals in this category, making up about 36.6% of the total workforce. While this is a notable portion, it highlights that females are in the minority within the organization. The presence of female employees, although less than their male counterparts, indicates an essential representation of gender diversity.

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Overall, the pie chart reveals a clear gender imbalance, with males forming nearly two-thirds of the employee base. This distribution highlights the need for potential strategies to promote gender diversity and inclusion within the organization. Efforts could include targeted recruitment, mentorship programs, and policies aimed at creating a more balanced and equitable workplace environment. The visual representation provides a straightforward understanding of the current gender dynamics and underscores areas for potential improvement in supporting a more diverse workforce.

Figure 18
Age distribution of employees

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 18 describes the distribution of employees across four distinct age groups. Each segment of the pie chart is color-coded to correspond with a specific age range and includes the number of employees within that range. The yellow segment, denoting the 46-63 age group, is the largest section of the pie chart, comprising 62 employees. This demonstrates that the majority of the workforce falls within this older age range, indicating a predominantly older employee demographic. The gray segment, which represents the 36-45 age group, is significantly larger than the previous two segments, including 13 employees. This indicates a noticeable increase in the number of employees who are in their late thirties to mid-forties. The orange segment, corresponding to the 26-35 age group, is slightly larger than the blue segment and accounts for 4 employees. This shows a marginally higher number of employees in their late twenties to mid-thirties, but still a small proportion of the total workforce. The blue segment, which represents the 18-25 age group, is the smallest portion of the chart, indicating that there are only 3 employees within this age range. This suggests that young adults make up a very small fraction of the workforce.

To sum it up, the pie chart reveals that the largest portion of employees are aged between 46 and 63 years, followed by a smaller but notable group of employees aged 36 to 45. The youngest age groups, 18-25 and 26-35, are minimally represented within the company's workforce.

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4.3. Current state of digitization

The company already works within daily operations in a digital way using shared MS Office documents for joint projects, issues invoices and reports signed electronically by using EDI and do its best to connect all suppliers and wholesale customers to this ecosystem. While communicating with them, online and video conferences started to be increasingly used via Microsoft Teams platform which offers also planning via shared calendars, that is also implemented in advanced technologies.

4.4. Employees' perception of the implementation of digital solutions

Figure 19

Employees' perception of the implementation of digital solutions

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 19 provides a visual description of employee experiences during the implementation of an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system within the organization. The chart is divided into three segments, each reflecting a different level of experience: smooth and effective, with complications, and very problematic and complicated. The largest segment, colored in orange, represents employees who experienced the implementation process "With complications." This segment includes 41 respondents, which accounts for approximately 50.6% of the total responses. This indicates that more than half of the employees encountered some challenges or issues during the ERP system implementation. These complications could range from technical difficulties to resistance to change, suggesting areas where the implementation process could be improved for smoother transitions in the future. The blue segment signifies employees who found the implementation to be "Smooth and effective." There are 38 respondents in this category, making up about 46.9% of the total responses. This substantial proportion indicates that a significant number of employees had a positive experience with the ERP implementation, finding it well-executed and beneficial.

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This group likely experienced minimal disruptions and found the system integration to be seamless, highlighting successful aspects of the process that can be replicated in future projects. The smallest segment, in grey, represents employees who found the implementation "Very problematic and complicated." This group includes 3 respondents, constituting roughly 3.7% of the total responses. This minimal percentage suggests that only a small fraction of the workforce faced severe difficulties during the ERP system implementation. These employees might have encountered major technical issues, significant disruptions, or inadequate support, indicating critical areas that need attention to prevent similar experiences in future implementations.

Overall, the pie chart reveals a mixed experience with the ERP system implementation. While nearly half of the employees found the process smooth and effective, a slightly larger portion encountered complications, and a small minority faced very problematic issues. This distribution highlights the importance of addressing the challenges faced by those who experienced complications and ensuring robust support and resources are available to facilitate successful ERP system implementations across the organization.

Figure 20

Changes in processes since the first start of Industry 4.0 technologies implementation

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 20 provides insights into employee perceptions regarding the impact of digitalization on organizational processes. The chart is segmented into three distinct categories: those who have noticed mostly negative changes, those who have not noticed any changes, and those who have noticed positive changes. The largest segment, colored in grey, represents employees who have noticed positive changes since the start of digitalization. This segment includes 49 respondents, which accounts for approximately 60.5% of the total responses.

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This substantial majority indicates that digitalization has been largely beneficial, with the majority of employees recognizing improvements in processes, increased efficiency, or enhanced capabilities as a result of digital initiatives. The blue segment signifies employees who perceive the changes as mostly negative. There are 25 individuals in this category, making up about 30.9% of the respondents. This significant minority indicates that nearly a third of the workforce has experienced challenges or adverse effects due to digitalization. These negative perceptions might be due to issues such as technical difficulties, increased complexity, or inadequate support during the transition. The smallest segment, in orange, represents employees who have not noticed any changes. This group includes 8 respondents, constituting roughly 9.9% of the total responses. This smaller percentage suggests that a minority of employees have either not been impacted by the digitalization efforts or are unaware of the changes implemented. This could indicate a need for better communication and engagement strategies to ensure all employees are informed and involved in the digital transformation process.

Overall, the pie chart reveals that while the majority of employees have noticed positive changes due to digitalization, a notable portion has experienced negative impacts, and a small group has not perceived any changes. This distribution highlights the varied experiences of employees and underscores the importance of addressing the challenges faced by those negatively impacted, as well as improving communication and support to maximize the benefits of digitalization for the entire organization.

Figure 21
Effectiveness of the current ERP system

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

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Figure 21 depicts employee perceptions of the ERP system's effectiveness within the organization. The chart is divided into three segments, each representing a different level of perceived effectiveness: ineffective, moderately effective, and very effective. The largest segment, colored in orange, represents employees who find the ERP system "Moderately effective." This segment includes 59 respondents, accounting for approximately 71.1% of the total responses. This significant majority indicates that while most employees find the ERP system beneficial, they also see space for improvement. The ERP system likely meets many of their needs but could be enhanced to better support their tasks and workflows. The grey segment signifies employees who find the ERP system "Very effective." There are 21 respondents in this category, making up about 25.3% of the total responses. This notable proportion suggests that a quarter of the employees are highly satisfied with the ERP system, finding it to be a valuable tool that effectively meets their requirements and improves their productivity. The smallest segment, in blue, represents employees who find the ERP system "Ineffective." This group includes 2 respondents, constituting roughly 2.4% of the total responses. This minimal percentage indicates that only a very small fraction of the workforce perceives the ERP system as not meeting their needs or expectations. These employees may be facing specific challenges or issues that need to be addressed to enhance their experience with the system.

Overall, the pie chart reveals that a majority of employees view the ERP system as moderately effective, with a significant portion considering it very effective and a small minority finding it ineffective. This distribution highlights the general satisfaction with the ERP system while pointing to opportunities for further enhancements to ensure it meets the diverse needs of all employees. Company adopted ERP system created in Slovakia aimed at food and beverage production industry, which introduces the optimization processes of managed warehouses and dispatches via mobile terminals in a company. The record of processes has moved to a higher level.

Figure 22 illustrates employee perceptions of how effectively the ERP system enhances process tracking and inventory management within the organization. The chart is divided into 3 segments: significantly improves overview, provides some benefits but is not ideal, and has minimal impact. The largest segment, colored in orange, represents employees who believe that the ERP system "Provides some benefits but is not ideal." This segment includes 51 respondents, accounting for approximately 63% of the total responses. This majority indicates that while most employees acknowledge certain advantages brought by the ERP system, they also recognize that there are areas where it falls short. This could suggest that the system partially meets their needs but has potential for further improvement to achieve optimal functionality. The blue segment signifies employees who feel that the ERP system "Significantly improves overview." There are 27 respondents in this category, making up about 33% of the total responses. This substantial proportion reflects that a notable minority of employees find the ERP system highly effective in enhancing their ability to track processes and manage inventory. These respondents likely experience considerable benefits in terms of efficiency, accuracy, and visibility into operations. The smallest segment, in grey, represents employees who perceive that the ERP system "Has minimal impact." This group includes 4 respondents, constituting roughly 4.9% of the total responses.

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This minimal percentage suggests that only a small fraction of the workforce sees little to no improvement from the ERP system in their process tracking and inventory management tasks. These employees may have specific challenges or may work in areas where the ERP system's capabilities are less pronounced.

Overall, the pie chart reveals a mixed perception of the ERP system's impact on process tracking and inventory management. While a significant majority sees some benefits, they also believe there is room for enhancement. Meanwhile, a substantial minority finds the system highly beneficial, and a small group perceives minimal impact. This distribution highlights the need for ongoing assessment and improvement of the ERP system to ensure it meets the diverse needs of all employees and maximizes its effectiveness across the organization.

Figure 22

Impact of the current ERP system on process tracking and inventory management

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 23 illustrates the perceived effects of implementing a cloud solution on work efficiency. The blue segment, representing "Provides some benefits but also has disadvantages," is the largest portion of the chart, indicating that 58 respondents believe the cloud solution offers some benefits but also comes with disadvantages. This suggests a balanced view where the benefits are recognized, but the disadvantages cannot be ignored. The gray segment, which represents "Significantly simplifies and accelerates processes," is a significant portion of the chart, representing 22 respondents. This indicates that a notable number of respondents believe the cloud solution significantly improves work efficiency by simplifying and accelerating processes. The orange segment, corresponding to "Has minimal impact," is a very small portion of the chart, representing 2 respondents. This shows that a very small number of respondents believe the cloud solution has a minimal impact on work efficiency.

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To sum it up, the pie chart reveals that the majority of respondents acknowledge that while the cloud solution provides some benefits, it also has disadvantages. A smaller, yet significant group believes that the cloud solution significantly improves work efficiency, while a very small number think it has minimal impact.

Figure 23
The impact of cloud solution on work efficiency

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 24
Utilization and reach of artificial intelligence

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

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Figure 24 describes how respondents have indicated the use of AI in their organization, with a total of 82 responses divided into various applications. Here is a detailed description of each segment regarding results from survey. The majority of respondents, 41 people making up 50%, indicated that AI is primarily used for demand prediction and production planning. This suggests that half of the AI applications focus on forecasting market demand and optimizing production schedules, which is important for maintaining efficiency and meeting market needs. The second most common use of artificial intelligence as described by 28 employees, that indicates 35% of responds is in optimizing logistics processes. This involves using AI to enhance the efficiency of supply chain management, reducing costs, and improving delivery times. Approximately 11% of respondents (9 people) noted that artificial intelligence is used to automate tasks in administration and support. This includes streamlining routine administrative functions and decreasing workload of human resources for more complex tasks and improving overall efficiency. A smaller portion, 3 employees what makes 4% of respondents stated, company use AI for providing personalized recommendations to customers.

This application aims to increase customer satisfaction by offering customized suggestions based on individual preferences and behaviors. Interestingly, none of the respondents indicated using AI to create and manage chatbots for customer service. This could mean a potential area for future improvement or a current lack of necessity in their operations. Notably, none of the respondents chose the option indicating they do not know how AI is utilized within their organization. This signifies that all participants are aware of the specific applications of AI in their workplace. The chart illustrates a strong emphasis on using artificial intelligence for operational efficiencies such as demand prediction and logistics optimization, while highlighting opportunities for further exploration in areas related to customer service automation.

5. Case study 4

5.1. Company background

This IT company was founded by two partners who are still managing the company on their own. The main objective is to provide outsource remote IT network management for SME companies in Slovakia and data migration to cloud solutions from Office 365. There are 30 IT specialists working in this company in various positions, which include IT support, senior IT administrator, IT support team leader, business development manager, sales manager and project manager. The company places great emphasis on excellent support for the customer, who after agreeing to cooperate gets a phone number and in the event of an outage, the situation is resolved 24 hours a day.

5.2. Employee demographics

Figure 25 provides a visual representation of the gender composition within the company. The chart is divided into two segments, depicting the number of male and female employees. The data reveals a significant gender imbalance among the employees, there are 27 male employees represented by a blue segment, making up the vast majority (96,43%) of the workforce. There is only 1 female employee within the company represented by orange color, what makes the rest 3,57% of total employees in company.

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Figure 25
Gender distribution of employees

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 26
Age distribution of employees

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 26 illustrates the distribution of employees across different age groups within the company. The chart is divided into four segments, representing the age ranges of 18-25, 26-35, 36-45, and 46-55 years. The biggest segment depicted by orange color is age group 26-35 years. This age group represents a substantial 89.29% of the workforce. The majority of the employees, 25 out of 28, fall within this age range, indicating a predominantly young workforce. Following segment depicted by gray color indicates employees in range 36-45 years old what makes 7.14% of the total employees and this group has a modest representation with 2 employees. There is only 1 employee younger than 25 years old, illustrated in blue segment and it constitutes 3.57% of the total workforce.

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To sum it up, the pie chart reveals a significant concentration of employees in the 26-35 age range, which accounts for 89.29% of the workforce, marked in orange. This indicates that the company's workforce is predominantly young, with minimal representation from other age groups. The 18-25 age group (blue) constitutes 3.57% of the employees, the 36-45 age group (gray) makes up 7.14%, and there are no employees in the 46-55 age range (yellow). This distribution highlights the company's youthful demographic and suggests potential areas for workforce diversification.

5.3. Current state of digitization

This company has properly operated in digital communication at the operative level as well as communication with customers and suppliers for several years. Whether it is digital documentation, creation of quotations, orders or paperless invoicing or communication via video calls, screen sharing and remote service, all these options add value and increase the increase.

Given that digitization is more about working in a paperless environment and using tools for remote work, in the case of Industry 4.0 concept, it is already necessary to think about the implementation of advanced analytics tools, interconnect them and know how to correctly interpret the outputs.

5.4. Employees' perception of the implementation of digital solutions

Figure 27

Employees' perception of the implementation of digital solutions

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 27t provides a visual representation of the different experiences employees had during the implementation of an ERP system in their company. The chart is divided into three categories: smooth and effective, with complications, and very problematic and complicated.

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17 employees found the implementation process to be very problematic and complicated. It depicted by gray color in diagram. This constitutes roughly 60.71% of the total responses, indicating that the majority of employees faced substantial challenges during the ERP system implementation. Orange segment represented by 10 employees show they experienced complications during the ERP implementation. This category makes up about 35.71% of the responses, showing that a significant portion of employees encountered some difficulties but managed to work through them. There is only 1 employee who reported that the implementation process was smooth and effective. This represents approximately 3.57% of the total responses, indicating that very few found the transition seamless.

The implementation of the ERP system was a challenging process for most employees. Approximately 60.71% of respondents reported that the process was very problematic and complicated, while 35.71% encountered some complications but managed to overcome them. Only a small fraction, about 3.57%, found the implementation to be smooth and effective. These findings highlight the importance of thorough planning, effective communication, and comprehensive training to mitigate difficulties during such transitions.

Figure 28

Changes in processes since the first start of Industry 4.0 technologies implementation

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 28 illustrates the responses from employees regarding the impact of digitalization on their work processes. The chart is divided into three segments, each representing different perceptions of these changes. The most respondents depicted by gray color, 15 out of 28 employees (approximately 53.57%), reported that they have noticed positive changes in their processes change since implementing of Industry 4.0 technologies began. Twelve employees depicted by blue color, what is approximately 42.86% of the total respondents, have noticed mostly negative changes in process change since the start technologies implementation. There is only one employee who did not perceive any changes.

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Figure 29

Effectiveness of the current ERP system

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 29 provides an overview of how employees perceive the effectiveness of the ERP system implemented in the company. The chart is divided into three segments, each representing different levels of perceived effectiveness: ineffective, moderately effective, and very effective. The largest segment, depicted by a gray color, indicates the employees who find the ERP system very effective. 14 respondents (50% of respondents) think that system is working effectively and it meets intended goals. The second largest segment is illustrated by orange color and indicates employees who find ERP system as moderately effective. Thirteen employees, making up 46.43% of the respondents, feel that the system works adequately but may have some areas for improvement. This group represents a substantial portion of the employees, suggesting that while the system is functional, it may not fully meet all expectations or potential. There is only one employee perceiving system as ineffective.

Company still has not finished implementing of ERP system developed in Czech Republic aimed at IT industry, which should introduce in the end the optimization processes of planning, cashflow prediction, service outages at client offices, predictive planning of IT technology orders from supplier warehouses and life cycle of a client.

Figure 30 provides details into how employees perceive the effectiveness of the ERP system in improving process tracking and inventory management. The chart is divided into three segments, each representing a different level of perceived impact: significantly improves overview, provides some benefits but is not ideal, and has minimal impact.

The orange segment signifies those who consider the ERP system to provide some benefits but believe it is not ideal. Fourteen employees, making up 50% of the respondents, feel that while the ERP system offers certain advantages, it can be improved. This segment represents half of the employees, suggesting that although the system is functional, it may not fully meet all needs or expectations.

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The blue segment shows employees who believe the ERP system significantly improves process tracking and inventory management. 11 employees, accounting for 39.29% of the total respondents are involved in this category. It indicates that a substantial portion of the workforce perceives the ERP system as highly effective in increasing their ability to track processes and manage inventory. The gray segment represents employees who find that the ERP system has minimal impact on process tracking and inventory management. Three respondents, what makes 10.71% of the total, perceive the system as not significantly enhancing these areas. This smaller portion of the workforce highlights that for some employees, the ERP system does not provide noticeable benefits.

To sum it up, 39.29% of employees think the system significantly improves these functions, half of the respondents (50%) believe it provides some benefits but is not ideal. A smaller group, 10.71%, feels the system has minimal impact. These responds suggest that while the ERP system is beneficial for many, there are opportunities for further enhancement to better meet the needs and expectations of all staff.

Figure 30

Impact of the current ERP system on process tracking and inventory management

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 31 depicts employees' perceptions of how cloud solutions have influenced their work efficiency. The chart is divided into 3 segments: significantly simplifies and accelerates processes, provides some benefits but also has disadvantages, and has minimal impact. The gray segment indicates employees who find that the cloud solution significantly simplifies and accelerates processes. 25 answers, constituting 89.29% of the total, perceive the system as greatly improving these areas. This overwhelming majority suggests that most employees have experienced significant improvements in efficiency due to the cloud solution.

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The blue segment provides perception of employees who believe that the cloud solution provides some benefits but also has disadvantages. 3 employees, accounting for 10.71% of the total respondents involve this category. This indicates that a small portion of the workforce acknowledges the advantages of the cloud solution while also recognizing its drawbacks.

To sum it up, approximately 89.29% of employees, feel that the cloud solution significantly simplifies and accelerates their work processes. A smaller group, around 10.71%, recognizes some benefits but also acknowledges disadvantages. No employees reported that the cloud solution has minimal impact. These insights suggest that while there are some perceived drawbacks, the overall impact of the cloud solution on work efficiency is viewed positively by most employees.

Figure 31

The impact of cloud solution on work efficiency

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 32 depicts utilization of different AI applications within the company. The chart is divided into 6 segments, each representing a specific AI use case: demand prediction and service planning, personalized recommendations for B2B, optimization of logistics processes, automation of tasks in administration and hotline, creating and managing chatbots for customer service, and those who do not know about AI usage. The yellow segment shows that the most of employees, 18 out of 28 respondents (64.29%), believe AI is mostly used for automating tasks in administration and hotline services. This dominant segment suggests that automation in administrative functions is the most recognized and impactful application of AI within the company. The light blue segment represents employees who see AI's primary role as creating and managing chatbots for customer service. 7 respondents, accounting for 25% of the total respondents are involved in this category, what indicates a significant recognition of AI in improving customer interactions through chatbots.

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The dark blue segment represents staff who believe that AI is primarily used for demand prediction and service planning. 2 employees, accounting for 7.14% of the total respondents, are involved in this category. This indicates that a smaller portion of the workforce sees AI's role in forecasting demand and planning services as very important. Orange segment, involving 1 employee represent utilization of AI in personalized recommendations for B2B. The gray segment shows that none of the respondents view AI as being used primarily for the optimization of logistics processes. This highlights that logistics optimization may not be a focal point for AI applications in the firm.

Figure 32
Utilization and reach of artificial intelligence

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

6. Case study 5

6.1. Company background

The bakery and sandwich market is strong industry of daily consumption. This firm is one of the leading producers of coated pastries, sandwiches, filled baguettes, panini and wraps in Slovakia, exporting its products to several EU countries. The company was founded in 2001 and today employs more than 400 employees. As part of its main activities, they operate its own bakery, which produces pastries on their own, and also operates vehicle fleet to ensure distribution to stores, gas stations, and sandwich machines.

6.2. Employee demographics

Figure 33 depicts the number of male and female employees within a company. According to the chart, there are 39 male employees which makes 55.7% of total workforce and 31 female

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employees that accounts for 44.3%. This distribution shows there is a relatively balanced workforce, with a slight majority of male employees compared to female employees. The chart effectively highlights the gender composition of the company, showing that while males constitute the majority, the difference is not overwhelming.

Figure 33
Gender distribution of employees

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 34
Age distribution of employees

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 34 provides overview of the workforce's age composition in the firm. The largest part in graph represented by the gray segment, shows that 44 employees fall within the 36-45 age range, what makes up approximately 62.9% of the total workforce. This indicates that the majority of the employees are in this middle age group. The orange segment represents the 26-

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35 age range, with 13 employees, which accounts for about 18.6% of the workforce. This segment highlights that a significant, but smaller, portion of employees are in their late twenties to mid-thirties. The yellow part of graph involves 11 employees aged 46-63, representing roughly 15.7% of the total workforce. This indicates that there is a notable presence of older employees, though they are not the majority. The blue segment representing the 18-25 age range, is the smallest group with only 2 employees. This group constitutes about 2.9% of the workforce, indicating that younger employees are the least represented age group in the company. To sum the results up, this pie chart shows a workforce predominantly composed of employees aged 36-45, with smaller proportions of employees in the younger and older age groups.

6.3. Current state of digitization

The company is ranked as innovative and its goal is constant growth thanks to modern technologies and processes. It has been using cloud solutions for document storage, safe backup of these documents, easy sharing and team work on projects for several years.

The company has been using the electronic data exchange system called EDI for several years. This acronym hides fully automated electronic exchange of business documents between business partners in a structured form from one application directly to another application based on generally agreed standards. It is significantly efficient, documents do not need to be printed or scanned, so invoices, orders, delivery notes, or contractual documents are exported in real time to external applications as well as imported from external applications. This process works both ways.

6.4. Employees' perception of the implementation of digital solutions

Figure 35

Employees' perception of the implementation of digital solutions

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

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Figure 35 shows an overview of the different experiences that respondents reported regarding the implementation process. The largest portion of respondents, represented by the blue segment, said their experience was "smooth and efficient." This group consists of 40 respondents, which represents approximately 57.1% of the total number. This indicates that more than half of the respondents found the implementation process easy and successful. The orange segment represents those who encountered complications during implementation. This group includes 24 respondents, which make up about 34.3% of the total number. This indicates that a significant proportion of respondents encountered some problems, although they were still able to proceed with implementation. The gray segment represents respondents who found the process "very problematic and complicated." This group includes 6 respondents, which represents about 8.6% of the total number. This smaller group suggests that while most respondents managed the transition, a few faced serious difficulties.

To sum it up, graph indicates that while the majority of respondents had a smooth and efficient experience implementing automated bakery production lines, a significant minority encountered complications or significant problems.

Figure 36

Changes in processes since the first start of Industry 4.0 technologies implementation

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 36 provides insights into employee perceptions regarding the impact of digitalization on organizational processes. The chart is segmented into three distinct categories: those who have noticed mostly negative changes, those who have not noticed any changes, and those who have noticed positive changes. The largest segment, colored in grey, represents employees who have noticed positive changes since the start of digitalization. This segment includes 49 respondents, which accounts for approximately 60.5% of the total responses.

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This substantial majority indicates that digitalization has been largely beneficial, with the majority of employees recognizing improvements in processes, increased efficiency, or enhanced capabilities as a result of digital initiatives. The blue segment signifies employees who perceive the changes as mostly negative. There are 25 individuals in this category, making up about 30.9% of the respondents. This significant minority indicates that nearly a third of the workforce has experienced challenges or adverse effects due to digitalization. These negative perceptions might be due to issues such as technical difficulties, increased complexity, or inadequate support during the transition. The smallest segment, in orange, represents employees who have not noticed any changes. This group includes 8 respondents, constituting roughly 9.9% of the total responses. This smaller percentage suggests that a minority of employees have either not been impacted by the digitalization efforts or are unaware of the changes implemented. This could indicate a need for better communication and engagement strategies to ensure all employees are informed and involved in the digital transformation process.

Overall, the pie chart reveals that while the majority of employees have noticed positive changes due to digitalization, a notable portion has experienced negative impacts, and a small group has not perceived any changes. This distribution highlights the varied experiences of employees and underscores the importance of addressing the challenges faced by those negatively impacted, as well as improving communication and support to maximize the benefits of digitalization for the entire organization.

Figure 37
Effectiveness of the current ERP system

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 37 describes how employees perceive the effectiveness of ERP system in their organization. The largest segment of respondents, represented by the gray segment, found the ERP system to be "Very effective." This group consists of 55 respondents, which accounts for approximately 78.6% of the total. This indicates that the majority of respondents believe that

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the ERP system is highly effective in meeting their needs. Orange colored segment represents those who consider the ERP system to be "Moderately effective." This group includes 14 respondents, making up about 20% of the total. This suggests that while the system is somewhat effective, there is possibility for improvement. The smallest segment, shown in blue, represents those who found the ERP system to be "Ineffective." This group consists of just 1 respondent, which translates to about 1.4% of the total. This indicates that very few respondents are dissatisfied with the system's performance. To sum it up, the chart reflects a generally positive perception of the ERP system, with the vast majority of respondents finding it either very effective or moderately effective in supporting their organizational needs.

The company adopted an ERP system created in Slovakia focused on the food industry. The main advantage of this complex solution is the overall summary of activities in the company across departments. Its excellent functionality improves business processes in the areas of finance, purchasing and warehouses, sales, shipping and production. It provides advanced planning methods, prioritization of production as well as optimization of the use of production capacities, purchasing and inventory.

Figure 38

Impact of the current ERP system on process tracking and inventory management

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 38 describes how respondents perceive the effectiveness of their ERP system in process tracking and inventory management. The largest segment of the chart, illustrated by orange color, indicates that 45 respondents believe the ERP system "Provides some benefits but is not ideal." This group accounts for approximately 64.3% of the total, suggesting that while the system offers some improvements, there is significant possibility for improvement. The blue segment represents 19 respondents who perceive the ERP system "Significantly improves

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overview," making up about 27.1% of the total. This indicates that over a quarter of the respondents find the system to be highly effective in increasing their ability to track processes and manage inventory. The smallest segment, shown in gray, represents 6 respondents who believe the ERP system "Has minimal impact," which accounts for about 8.6% of the total. This suggests that a small minority find the system to be largely ineffective in these areas.

Overall, the chart reveals that while the ERP system is generally seen as beneficial, the majority of respondents believe that it could be more effective in improving process tracking and inventory management.

Figure 39

The impact of cloud solution on work efficiency

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 39 depicts how respondents perceive the effectiveness of a cloud solution in increasing their work processes. The largest group of respondents, shown in blue, represents 42 respondents who believe that the cloud solution "Provides some benefits but also has disadvantages." This group makes up approximately 60% of the total, indicating that while the cloud solution offers advantages, there are also notable drawbacks that limit its overall effectiveness. The second group depicted by gray color indicates that 18 respondents feel the cloud solution "Significantly simplifies and accelerates processes," accounting for about 25.7% of the total. This suggests that over a quarter of the respondents find the cloud solution highly effective in boosting work efficiency. The orange segment represents 10 respondents who believe the cloud solution "Has minimal impact," which constitutes about 14.3% of the total. This indicates that a smaller portion of the respondents do not see significant improvements in work efficiency from the cloud solution.

To sum it up, the chart reveals that while the cloud solution is generally seen as beneficial, the majority of respondents acknowledge its disadvantages, with only a quarter finding it significantly impactful in simplifying and accelerating processes.

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Figure 40
Utilization and reach of artificial intelligence

Source: authors' calculations based on the data collected

Figure 40 describes how respondents perceive using of AI in a company regarding different options. The largest portion of the chart, represented by the blue segment, shows that 41 respondents use AI for "Demand prediction and production planning." This group makes up approximately 58.6% of the total, what indicates the majority of respondents rely on AI to forecast demand and optimize production schedules. The gray segment represents 16 respondents who are using AI for "Optimization of logistics processes," which accounts for about 22.9% of the total. This suggests that a significant portion of respondents are focusing on improving the efficiency of firm logistics through AI.

The orange segment, representing "Personalized recommendations for customers," includes 5 respondents, making up about 7.1% of the total. This indicates that a smaller group is leveraging AI to enhance customer personalization. The yellow segment, which accounts for 8 respondents, represents the use of AI for the "Automation of tasks in administration and support." This group makes up about 11.4% of the total, showing that some respondents are using AI to streamline administrative functions. No respondents reported using AI for "Creating and managing chatbots for customer service" or selected "I do not know," with both categories representing 0% of the total responses.

Overall, the chart demonstrates that AI is primarily used for demand prediction and logistics optimization, with less emphasis on customer personalization and administrative automation.

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